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Tattvārthasūtra: Propagation of multilateral thoughts by the Jinas through the accommodation of all ideas from the perspective of Anekāntavāda

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Summary

Anekāntavāda is one of the major proponents of Jainism. Like many other concepts it has become a propeller to make Jain philosophy a special one in the world. It is a manifold doctrine of the Jain *Tīrthaṅkaras* and full of intellectual flavors of Indian metaphysics. It should be noteworthy for the present world as it shuns the *rigidity and stubbornness of unilateralism* in faith-based understandings, *monolithic beliefs or doctrines* and at the same time *monoculturalism*. In today's world when religious tolerance is becoming fragile and the application of logic before accepting and propagating religion is gradually disappearing or becoming parochial or prejudiced, the idea of *Anekāntavāda* can be a very good resort to mitigate the ideological intolerance. *Tattvārthasūtra* is a quasi-canonical text, developed on the basis of *Anekāntavāda* written in Sanskrit by Ācārya Umaswami . The incumbent essay wants to reexamine *Tattvārthasūtra* which as a sequel of *Anekāntavāda*. The essay wants to review its necessity and to find out the gamut of its applicability to generate ideological tolerance and thus to create a peaceful world, where people of all faiths and ideologies could coexist in a harmonious ambiance.

Jinas and Tīrthaṅkaras in Jainism

Without understanding the concepts of Jina and *Tīrthaṅkara*, it is quite difficult to understand *Anekāntavāda* and *Tattvārthasūtra*. Historically Jainism developed as a part of the *Śramaṇa movement* of India. The term *Jina* is very important to fathom the Jain *Śramaṇic tradition*. Despite the major sectarian or denominational differences there is enough common

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ground among Jain groups that one may legitimately speak of 'Jainism' and the people who can be considered to be 'Jains'. The term Jain emerged from the term Jina, which means 'victor' or 'conqueror.' But in Jainism Jina refers to someone, who has established his complete victory over attachments and aversions. A Jain is someone who reveres and follows the personages considered to be the Jinās and regards their teachings as authoritative. This is the *sine qua non* of all forms of Jainism. The concept Jina is invariably of great importance in Jainism and the Jain traditions. One may think that Jainism's emphasis on nonviolence might foster mere meekness or docility. But in Jainism the Jina is a victorious one, who might have been—had he so chosen to be—a worldly king and a conqueror of the world. But instead, the Jina becomes a spiritual king and transposes the venue of war from the outer field of battle to an inner one (Babb 1996: 5).

The Jinās are also called the *Tīrthāṅkaras*. The term *Tīrthāṅkara* means 'one who establishes a *tīrtha*.' Tīrth has two meanings; it primarily means 'ford' or 'crossing a place.' In this sense the *Tīrthāṅkara* is one, who establishes a ford across what is often called (by Hindus as well as Jains) 'the ocean of existence.' The term also refers to the community, established by a *Tīrthāṅkara*, or the ascetics and laity, who put his teachings into practice. Hence such a community itself is motivated and engaged to cross a place (i.e. the mundane life) to be liberated. But it is to be noted that a *Tīrthāṅkara* is a human being, although he is an extraordinary one, who has conquered the attachments and aversions that stand in the way of liberation from worldly bondages. By means of his own efforts, and entirely without the benefit of being taught by others, he has achieved that state of omniscience, in which all things are known to him: past, present and future. But before final attainment of own liberation, the *Tīrthāṅkara* imparts his self-gained liberating knowledge to others so that they might become victors too. Thus, he establishes a crossing passage for other beings (Babb 1996: 5-6).

The great personages, who go by both appellations 'Jina' and '*Tīrthāṅkara*', are the central figures for all denominations and forms of Jainism. Not only are their teachings central to Jainism but they themselves are also Jainism's principal revered persons and hence their images, icons and idols are widely revered in the Jain temples (*Jinalayas*). However, it is crucial to know for the students of the Jain studies that the Jinās i.e. the *Tīrthāṅkaras* after their departure are not believed to interact with their worshipers in our sense. This is because they are no longer present in our part of the cosmos. They followed a specific trajectory; they came, achieved their omniscience, imparted their teachings to the disciples and learners and

then departed. And after their departing they became completely *liberated beings*. Hence, they have ceased to interact with the worldly actions and attachments. They dwell forever at the apex of the cosmos in an omniscient condition and rest there totally in an isolated bliss. But it is also true that their former presence left indelible impacts in the world. With their teachings they also created a social order through a community (i.e. *Caturvidh Sangh*) consisting of four great categories: *Sadhus* (monks), *Sadhvis* (nuns), *Sravaks* (laymen) and *Sravikas* (laywomen). The monks and nuns are those who are directly commissioned to exemplify the teachings of the *Tīrthāṅkaras* in their everyday's life. The term *Sravak* and its feminine counterpart *Sravika* mean the 'listener.' Here we can deduce that the *Sravaks* and the *Sravikas* are those who hear the teachings of the *Tīrthāṅkaras*. The *Tīrthāṅkaras* also left behind them a kind of metaphysical echo of welfare (*Kalyan*) generated by their presence that continues to reverberate in the cosmos and that can be mobilized by rituals and some other ways at a particular time (Cort 1989: 421-22).

According to the Jain cosmology an infinity number of *Tīrthāṅkaras* already came and went in the universe (Dundas 2002: 20). Indeed, there are *Tīrthāṅkaras*' teachings are running in other regions of the cosmos as in ours at the present time. In our region twenty-four *Tīrthāṅkaras* have appeared over the course of the current cosmic period. The last of them was Mahāvīra, who lived, taught, and achieved liberation some 2,500 years ago. In our world there will be no more *Tīrthāṅkara* until after the next cosmic time-cycle has begun. The twenty-four *Tīrthāṅkaras* who have come and gone in our region are the principal beings represented by images and worshiped by image-worshipping Jains. It is true that the Jains also worship deities who are not *Tīrthāṅkaras*. But in fact their worship is entirely subordinate to the worship of the *Tīrthāṅkaras* (Babb 1996: 6-7).

In the Jain cosmology the wheel of time is divided in two halves: *Utsarpiṇī* or ascending time cycle and *Avasarpiṇī*, the descending time cycle. Each consists of 10 x 1 crore x 1 crore *Addhāsāgaropama* (10 kotikotī *Sāgaropama*). Thus, one cycle of time (*Kalpakāla*) gets over in 20 *kotikotī Sāgaropama* (Samantabhadra 2016: 71). The current one is an *Avasarpiṇī*. In each half of the cosmic time cycle exactly twenty-four *Tīrthāṅkaras* grace this part of the universe. The first *Tīrthāṅkara* in this present time cycle (*Hunda Avasarpiṇī*) was *Ṛṣabhadeva*, who is credited for formulating and organizing human beings to live in a society harmoniously. The 24th and the last *Tīrthāṅkara* of the present half-cycle was Mahāvīra (599 BC–527 BC). It is even recorded in the modern history that Mahāvīra and his

predecessor, Pārśvanātha, the twenty-third Tīrthaṅkara existed in the world (Zimmer 1953: 182-183).

So we can surmise that other *Tīrthaṅkaras* might have lived in the world as well.

Anekāntavāda: the idea of non-absolutism propagated by the Jinas

The Jain principles like nonviolence (*Ahiṃsā*), non-attachment (*Aparigraha*) and non-absolutism (*Anekāntavāda*) are relatively *nonanthropocentric concepts* of humanity related to nature, which attract people to embrace Jain path as a way of life. At the same time, one does not have to be a Jain inevitably in all cases in order to learn valuable lessons from Jainism (D Long 2009: XVI). The individualistic and experimental ways to attain truth evident in the life of both Mahāvīra and the Buddha, which resembled and later developed as two approaches through the Jain and Buddhist teachings respectively: *Anekāntavāda* and *Pratītyasamutpāda*. Both infer the multi-faceted nature of truth and the idea of interdependent origination. They have a clear postmodern ring, if we translate the sense from today's understanding (D Long 2009: 75). Mathieu Boisvert deduced from the very facts that the *Pratītyasamutpāda*, commonly translated as dependent origination or dependent arising, is a key Buddhist doctrine shared by all schools of Buddhism. It states that all *Dharmas* (phenomena) arise in dependence upon other Dharmas: 'if this exists, that exists; if this ceases to exist, that also ceases to exist'. The basic principle is that all things (Dharmas, phenomena, principles) arise in dependence upon other things (Boisvert 1996: 6-7).

In fact, *Anekāntavāda* - a fundamental doctrine of Jainism, is very important to understand the Jain ontology and soteriology. The Jain equivalent of the Hindu universalism can be found in the modern recovery by Jain intellectuals in the ancient teachings of *Anekāntavāda*, which manifest the doctrine of the multi-faceted character of reality. *Anekāntavāda* infers that any given topic can be viewed from a variety of valid perspectives. Only an enlightened Jina is capable of perceiving the whole truth of the matter or the fact (D Long 2009: 76). Hence, we can deduce that any single or any specific statement cannot describe the nature of existence and the *absolute truth*. This absolute knowledge i.e. the pure infinite knowledge or *Keval Gyan* is comprehended only by the *Arihants*. Other beings and their statements about absolute truth are incomplete, and they are at best some partial truths (Padmanabh S.1998: 91). Hence this doctrine says that all epistemic claims must be qualified in many ways, even including being affirmed and denied. It is to be noted that an Arihant is a *Jiva* (soul) who has conquered inner passions such as attachments, angers, prides and

greeds. He has destroyed four inimical *Karmas* and realized his pure self. *Arihants* are also called *Kevalins* (omniscient beings) because they possess *Keval Gyan* (the pure infinite knowledge). An *Arihant* is also called a *Jina* (victor or conqueror). At the end of his life an *Arihant* destroys remaining *Karmas* and subsequently attain *Mokṣa* (liberation); thus he becomes a *Siddha*. Those who become *Arihantas* have a body, while the *Siddhas* are bodiless pure spirit. The *Ṇamōkāra mantra*, the fundamental prayer dedicated to *Pañca-Parameṣṭhi* (five supreme beings), begins with *Ṇamō arihantāṇam* i.e. the obeisance to the *Arihants*.

These five supreme beings are:

Arihant: The awakened soul who has attained *Keval Gyan*(*Kevala Jñāna*) is considered to be an *Arihant*. The twenty-four *Tīrthaṅkaras* or *Jinas*, the revered founding figures of Jainism, are the *Arihants* in the present time cycle. All *Tīrthaṅkaras* are *Arihants* but all *Arihants* are not *Tīrthaṅkaras*.

Siddha (Ashiri): They are the souls, who have been liberated from the birth and death cycle. A *Siddha* is one, who has attained *Siddhi* i.e. the power of performing paranormal capabilities (White, Dominik 2012: 34).

Acarya (*Ācārya*): An *Ācārya* is the head of the ascetic order. Some of the noted *Achāryas* are Bhadrabahu, Kundakunda, Samantabhadra, Umaswami, Sthulibhadra etc.

Upadhyaya: An *Upadhyaya* is a preceptor or a teacher, who perceives and then teaches to enlighten his pupils.

Muni or *Jain monks*: The Jain monasticism refers to the order of monks and nuns in the Jain community and is divided into two major denominations: the *Digambara* and the *Śvētāmbara*. Although the monastic practices of the two major denominations vary to a great extent, the major principles of them are identical. Five *Mahāvratas* (Great Vows) from *Mahāvīra*'s teachings are invariably followed by all Jain ascetics. Historians believe that a united Jain *Sangha* (community) existed 367 BCE, about 160 years after the *Mokṣa*, i.e. the liberation of great *Mahavira* (Padmanabh S.1998: 163).

According to the Jains every soul has the potential to become an *Arihant*. A soul which destroys all *Kashayas* i.e. the inner enemies like anger, ego, deception and greed, responsible for the perpetuation of ignorance, becomes an *Arihant* (Sangave 2001: 15). On the other hand, *Kevalins* i.e. the omniscient beings are of two kinds:

Tīrthaṅkara Kevalī: Twenty-four human spiritual guides, who are greatly concerned with the liberation of all human beings. So, after attaining omniscience they started to teach

them the path of salvation. It is to be noted that it is a premise of the Jain belief, only through the life of a human being the sentient beings can attain liberation. Nonsentient beings are always soulless (*Ajīva*) and as they cannot accumulate Karmas, no locomotion takes place for them in the Karmic universe. As a result, nothing takes place for their transformation i.e. their upgradation or degradation in the sentient universe. It has some similarity with the *Bodhisattva* concept of the *Mahāyāna Buddhism*. A Bodhisattva is anyone, who has generated *Bodhicitta* i.e. a spontaneous wish and a compassionate mind in order to attain *Buddhahood* for the benefit of all sentient beings (The Bodhisattva Vow: A Practical Guide to Helping Others 1995).

Sāmānya Kevalī: The *Kevalins*, who are concerned with their own liberation only.

The views of two sects of Jainism, *Digambara* (sky-clad) and *Śvētāmbara* (white-clad) differ on the subject of *Kevalins*. According to the Digambaras, a *kevalin* does not experience hunger or thirst, whereas the Śvētāmbaras believe that a Kevalin has normal human needs. He also travels and preaches. The Digambaras believe that they do not act in the normal sense of the word. They sit motionless in *Padmāsana* and their bodies emit *Divyadhvani*, a sacred sound which is interpreted by their followers as the fundamental truth (Dundas 2002: 45).

In the second *Upanga Agama* i.e. the *Rājaprasānīya*, there is a dialogue between Kesi, a disciple of Pārśva, and Payasi, a materialist king. In this dialogue we have discovered that Kesi proved to the king the existence of Jīva and its ability to obtain *Kevala Jñana* (Flügel 2006: 113).

Anekāntavāda and the idea of Jain relativity

Jeffery D Long elaborately discussed on Jain contributions to South Asian religious thought especially its relevance to mitigate today's interreligious conflicts. The complex three Jain doctrines that refute the doctrinal bigotries and absolutism have been called by Jeffery the Jain '*doctrines of relativity*'. The first and foremost of these doctrines is *Anekāntavāda*, which claims that reality is complex, or *Anekānta* (literally means *non-one-sided*). We have discussed it slightly above. It deals with the intrinsic nature of existence and conceptualizes a corollary: The entities cannot be reduced to a single characteristic or concept, reality being irreducibly complex. Hence, we can embark upon the second doctrine, *Nayavāda*. It is named by D Long the '*doctrine of perspectives*'. This is an epistemic corollary of the first one – the nature of knowledge in the complex universe that *Anekāntavāda* posits. As the nature of reality is complex, anything may be known from a variety of *Nayas* or perspectives, which correspond to its multiple aspects. Hence this finally implies the third doctrine – *Syādvāda* or

the ‘*doctrine of conditional predication*’ (named by D Long, but it literally means the ‘*maybe doctrine*’). According to this doctrine the truth of any claim that one makes about a particular topic is dependent upon the related perspective, or *Naya*, from which the claim has been made. A claim can be true in one sense or from one perspective (the technical meaning of the Sanskrit verb ‘*Syāt*’ from the Jain philosophical context), false from another perspective, both true and false from another, although it may have an inexpressible truth-value from yet another etc (D Long 2009: 117).

D Long (2009) wrote, “Given the complex nature of reality, the fact that it can be approached from many partially – though not equally or fully – correct perspectives, and that the truth of our claims depends on the perspective we take, an attitude of openness and toleration toward various views is recommended (p. 116).”

In order to make the gist of these doctrines tangible D Long mentioned the famous allegory of the blind men and their elephant visit, which actually attributed to Siddhartha Gautama first, i.e. the Buddha. One day several blind men are brought before a king and asked to describe an elephant. An elephant is brought to them and they proceeded to feel it with their hands. One who grasps the elephant’s trunk claims that an elephant is like a snake. Another grasping a leg claims it is like a tree. Yet another grasps the tail and says it is like a rope. Another feeling the elephant’s one side claims it is like a wall. The blind men then proceed to argue amongst themselves about the true shape of the elephant. The moral of the story is that all blind men are partially correct. An elephant, indeed, possesses all the shapes that the blind men attribute to it. Everyone is partially incorrect, inasmuch as he denies the claims of the others (The earliest account of this story is from the Theravāda Buddhist Pāli Canon; *Udāna* 6.4:66–69).

From the Jain corollary only someone like a Jina, who can see the whole elephant, is in a position to say unequivocally, how the true shape of an elephant is. The rest of us are like the blind men, as we do not see ‘the true reality’ and ‘the whole’ as well. We can only say with certainty that we can conceive from our limited perceptions, although we deny that we cannot apprehend due to our limited sight.

However, the Jain doctrines of relativity do not constitute a form of *relativism* from the western viewpoint. A fully sighted person i.e. an omniscient Jina is certainly capable of apprehending the true nature of anything. This is very different from the conventional western relativism, which is deeply skeptic about the ability of a human being, if a human being really knows anything with certainty.

The doctrines of relativity are very much related to the claim of being omniscience of Mahāvīra mentioned in the Jain scriptures. In these texts Mahāvīra is shown answering profound metaphysical questions (considered ‘unanswerable’, or *Avyākata* in the Buddhist tradition) with both ‘yes’ and ‘no’, depending upon the perspective of the questioner. The soul is both eternal (in its intrinsic nature) and non-eternal (from the perspective of the karmic changes that it is constantly undergoing); the cosmos is both eternal (in the sense that it has no beginning or end and as such) and non-eternal (inasmuch as it passes through arising and descending cycles) and so on. Another rationale for these doctrines is to be found in the complex nature of the soul, which is true for all living entities. The soul has an unchanging, intrinsic nature; but it also experiences the *karmically* conditioned states. These come into being, exist for a while, and then pass away. According to the famous formula of *Tattvārthasūtra* 5:29, *utpādavyāyadhrauvyayuktam sat* – ‘emergence, perishing and endurance characterize [all] entities.’ In other words, there is a sense in which all things come to be, perish and endure. Later in the post-canonical Jain philosophical texts this understanding of reality caused an endlessly debate between the Buddhists and the Brahmins regarding the nature of reality, whether soul is permanent or impermanent. Contrasting themselves with the Buddhists, who upheld a doctrine of radical impermanence, and the Brahmins, who – particularly in the Advaita Vedānta tradition – upheld a doctrine of permanence, the Jains claimed that entities/souls are both permanent and impermanent in different senses and from different perspectives (D Long 2009: 119).

Jain philosophers thus believe that they have been able to present ‘*the true middle path*’ between the ever-warring philosophical camps of the Buddhists and the Brahmins and claim the metaphysical high ground in terms of being able to integrate the perspectives of the other two into their own. Historically the Jain doctrines of relativity were a tool for affirming their superiority of the Jain perspective over others. But the potential utility of the doctrines of relativity in resolving disputes between seemingly incompatible philosophies has led to the popular contemporary view that these doctrines are an extension of the Jain commitment to *Ahiṃsā* in the realm of the intellectual discourse. But this fact is historically dubious as the characterization of these doctrines renders them attractive as a way to address the issue of how to remain committed to a particular tradition while also being open to the views of others. They provide an argument for *religious pluralism*, the view that there is truth in many traditions, and not only in one. D Long also asserts (2009), “If they are simply describing different aspects of the same reality, though, like the blind men trying to give an account of

the elephant, then the idea that they are all true – not in the same sense, but in various senses and to varying degrees – can be defended (p. 119-120).”

Relativity in the view of Śvetāmbara Āgamas: Mahāvīra’s middle path and a comparison with the Buddhism.

A common problem faced by both the Buddha and Mahāvīra, according to the texts of their respective communities, was a set of Avyākata i.e. the unanswerable questions both from metaphysical and cosmological grounds, which raised controversies among the various schools of thought at that time.

As we read from the early Buddhist literature, the Buddha often refused to answer some questions considering them not to be conducive to liberation. But when he chose a method called the *Vibhajya* i.e. the analytical method in order to answer the questions, this involved clarifying the assumptions on the basis of which questions were posed. According to B.K. Matilal the Jain doctrines of relativity developed from a similar strategy on the part of Mahāvīra (Matilal 1981: 19-29).

The Buddhist *Majjhimanikāya (Cūlamālunkya Sutta)* lists the Avyākata questions as follows:

- 1) Is the *loka* (world, man) eternal?
- 2) Is the *loka* not eternal?
- 3) Is it (the *loka*) finite (with an end)?
- 4) Is it not finite?
- 5) Is that which is the body the soul? (Is the soul identical with the body?)
- 6) Is the soul different from the body?
- 7) Does the *Tathāgata* [the Buddha, a liberated being] exist after death?
- 8) Does he not exist after death?
- 9) Does he both exist and not exist after death?
- 10) Does he neither exist nor not exist after death? (Matilal 1981: 12)

The Buddha’s approach to the Avyākata can be seen as an attempt to avoid philosophical extremes in order to walk through a ‘*middle path*’ among the various currents of thoughts during his time. He simply refused to answer the first four questions, which are concerned with the beginning and the end of the world. The fifth and sixth questions, regarding the identity or non-identity/ non-self of the soul and the body that he addressed with his *Anātman* doctrine, denied an independent existing soul from the perspective of materialism or physicalism. The remaining questions he answered by negation.

Matilal suggests that the Jain doctrines of relativity developed from an analogous strategy on the part of Mahāvīra for dealing with the same set of questions. Unlike the Buddha, however, Mahāvīra replied to these questions in the affirmative, by answering them with a qualified ‘Yes’ rather than a ‘No’ – an approach taken by Jains to demonstrate Mahāvīra’s omniscience because his profound knowledge of all aspects of reality is not an alleged idea but a premise of the Jain faith. Matilal characterizes this approach as an “*inclusive middle path*” in contrast with the Buddhist “*exclusive middle path*”.

The Buddha avoided exclusive attachment to views by rejecting all of them. Mahāvīra avoided such attachment by incorporating all views equally into his own by generation a holistic view. His positive use of *Vibhajya* i.e. the analysis of the questions into their components parts was illustrated in the *Bhagavatī Sūtra*:

[T]he Venerable Mahāvīra told the Bhikkhu Jamāli thus: ... [T]he world is, Jamāli, eternal. It did not cease to exist at any time. It was, it is and it will be. It is constant, permanent, eternal, imperishable, indestructible, always existent.

The world is, Jamāli, non-eternal. For it becomes progressive (in time-cycle) after being regressive. And it becomes regressive after becoming progressive.

The soul is, Jamāli, eternal. For it did not cease to exist at any time. The soul is, Jamāli, non-eternal. For it becomes animal after being a hellish creature, becomes a man after becoming an animal and it becomes a god after being a man (Bhagavatī Sūtra 9:386; Translation by Matilal 1981: 19).

According to Jain tradition, an enlightened being or a Kevalin like Mahāvīra being omniscient is able to see the complexity of reality from all perspectives, and thus answer metaphysical questions from all of the various relatively valid points of view. Hence Mahāvīra posited that from the perspective of permanence the universe is eternal. On the contrary, from the perspective of change the universe is affirmed to be ‘non-eternal’ (D Long 2009:122).

Hence due to its intrinsic qualities the soul is eternal. As a result ‘it did not cease to exist any time.’ But from the perspective of its ever-changing, *karmically* determined experiences of *Samsāra*, and its rebirths in numerous different forms, the soul is non-eternal. The crux of the view is, the omniscient one’s sight encompasses all perspectives. Mahāvīra thus addressed the Avyākata questions and answered according to their various dimensions.

Mahāvīra’s omniscience underscores the importance of the existence of a unique, absolute perspective (another translation of Kevala is ‘unique’) for the Jain philosophy from which the relative validity of all other perspectives can be perceived and proclaimed. This

absolute perspective is the transcendental foundation, the necessary condition for the possibility, which constitutes the relativity of the Jain philosophy (D Long 2009:122).

It is ultimately a faith-based relativism rooted in the belief of the omniscient Kevalins rather than in the reasons alone. However even the later Jain philosophers did not revert from the idea of the necessity of an absolute perspective while forming the logic of their philosophy of relativity. The omniscience of the Jinas is their foremost priority.

Umāsvāti's *Tattvārthasūtra* and the metaphysical foundation of relativism

The Jain *Āgamas* do not affirm a simple and systematic presentation of the worldview of Mahāvīra and his immediate followers i.e. the *Ganadharas*. On the contrary, the texts include a wide variety of materials, ranging from biographical accounts of Mahāvīra and other *Tīrthāṅkaras*, cosmological treatises, minutely detailed accounts of the kinds of beings that exist in the world (including a variety of microscopic organisms), extensive treatments of ethics, monastic discipline, physiology, astrology, collections of prayers, narratives about gods and demons, detailed accounts of the various kinds of Karma, and discourses on metaphysical and epistemological issues (D Long 2009: 123).

The systematization of Jain doctrine was left to Umāsvāti, the tradition has preserved virtually no information on him, either historical or hagiographical (Dundas 2002: 86–87). Probably he lived between the second and the fifth century of the Common Era, when a variety of Indian philosophical schools began to coalesce and enter into extensive debates with one another. Umāsvāti composed the first known Jain doctrinal treatise in Sanskrit, the *Tattvārthasūtra*. It means “*On the Nature [artha] of Reality [tattva]*.” This was the raging Buddhist period, when the Buddhists monks began to write the Sanskrit *Sūtras*. Through writing in Sanskrit the Jains and the Buddhists could engage Brahmanical schools of thought in debates rather than remaining isolated with their respective *Ardha-Māgadhi* and *Pāli* worlds. These inscrutable languages were only understood by them.

The *Tattvārthasūtra* took ideas from the *Ardha-Māgadhi* canons (and in the Digambara *Satkhandāgama*), summarized them concisely and translated many of them to discuss the Indian philosophies of the time broadly. It contributed in giving an explicit and systematic expression to the fundamental metaphysical assumptions and implicit expression in the doctrines of the early Jain community. The discourses attributed to Mahāvīra in the canons. As an early systematic formulation of the Jain metaphysical position, this text became a

touchstone for all future Jain philosophical discourses. As a result, its definitions and characterizations of issues earned ‘quasi-scriptural status.’

Most relevant to the Jain philosophy of relativity is this text’s systematization of the concepts of *Satsāmānya*, *Niksepa*, and *Naya*. *Satsāmānya* means ‘existence-’ or ‘being-universal’. It refers to the general characteristics of everything that exists. These are, according to Umāsvāti, “emergence, perishing, and duration (Tattvārthasūtra 5:29).”

The importance of this Jain theory has to do with the character of the soul or *Jīva*, and the process of its liberation, which contrasts with the Brahmanical tradition. It affirms the ultimate permanence of Brahman as the underlying ground of reality. But Buddhism affirms radical impermanence of existence.

Jainism affirms the coexistence of permanence and impermanence, similarity and difference in the nature of the *Jīvas*. A *Jīva* is held to be permanent in one sense. It is eternally possessing infinite bliss, energy, perception and knowledge. But in a different sense it is also impermanent as much as its karmic accretions are in a state of constant flux. In contrast to Brahmanical and Buddhist tendencies toward *Māyāvāda* – a teaching which relegates either change or permanence, respectively, to the realm of illusion – the Jains affirm a metaphysical realism, which ensures that both change and continuity are fundamental.

The pluralistic character of reality that Jainism affirms, claim that a variety of entities (*dravyas*) constitute the world and these entities have a variety of aspects and as a result it raises or can raise variety of perspectives as well, from which all issues can be addressed. The perspectivism that this view entails was systematized by Umāsvāti through the interrelated concepts of *Niksepa* and *Naya*.

A *Niksepa*, or ‘gateway of investigation’, is a topic in terms of which an entity can be analyzed. Umāsvāti lists the *Niksepas* as *Nāma* (name), *Sthāpanā* (symbol), *Dravya* (potentiality), *Bhāvatā* (actuality), *Nirdeśa* (definition), *Svāmitva* (possession), *Sādhana* (cause), *Adhikarana* (location), *Sthiti* (duration), *Vidhānatā* (variety), *Sat* (existence), *Samkhyā* (numerical determination), *Ksetra* (field occupied), *Sparśana* (field touched), *Kāla* (continuity), *Antara* (time-lapse), *Bhāva* (states), and *Alpabahutva* (relative size) (Translation by Tatia, quoted from Umāsvāti 1994, p. 7–12).

Each *Niksepa* addresses different questions about the entity. What is it called? How can it be represented? What are its potential and actual states? How is it defined in terms of its relations to other entities? What qualities does it possess? What is the cause of its existence? Where is it? How long will it exist? Are there different types of this thing? And which of these types is it? Does it actually exist? How many things of this kind are there?

How much space does it fill? With what other things is it in contact? Does it exist continuously? How long will it stay in the particular state remaining in it? What state does exist in it? How big is it compared to other entities of its kind (D Long 2009:125)?

Nayas are philosophical perspectives from which a particular topic can be viewed and its conclusions can be determined. Umāsvāti lists seven views— *Naigamanaya* (common view), *Samgrahanaya* (generic view), *Vyavahāranaya* (pragmatic view), *Rjusūtranaya* (linear view), *Śabdanaya* (verbal view), *Samabhirūdhanaya* (etymological view) and *Evambhūtanaya* (actuality view). The common view is how an entity is generally perceived – what one might call a ‘common sense’ or an ‘unrefined perspective’. A generic view seeks to classify the entity. A pragmatic view assesses the entity in terms of its possible uses. A linear view looks at the entity as it is in the present moment. A verbal view seeks to name the entity. An etymological view uses this name and its relations with other words to discern its nature. And an actuality view is concerned with the concrete particulars of the entity.

Umāsvāti’s commentators see the *Nayas* as partial views collectively making up a valid cognition (*Pramāna*). But the concept of *Naya* underwent extensive elaboration in the later Jain philosophical texts, so that several variants of this concept now exist.

Conclusion

From Umāsvāti’s *Tattvārthasūtra* we can have a purview of relativism in Jain philosophy, which was embedded by *Anekāntavāda* and later from the canonical through the quasi canonical texts the philosophical arguments were reified and ramified as well. These arguments dissolved the unilateral and obdurate understandings of reality, world and the whole. Therefore, the arguments give space to reconsider the thought ventures and recast the possibilities of insight development. The threads of multiple thinking and accommodation of pluralism are vibrant in the arguments. The principles of *Anekāntavāda* and *Syādvāda* have found practical applications in almost all spheres of life such as personal, family, social and political (national and international) relations and led to the concepts of mutual respect, compromise, tolerance and forgiveness for each other’s views and it is essential for coexistence and harmonious living. These aspects have been discussed by Acharya Mahaprajna (2010), Mukherjee (1994) and others in numerous books, essays and articles. We have only considered here *Tattvārthasūtra*’s philosophical possibilities to mitigate ideological intolerance from the connection of *Anekāntavāda*.

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